

REVISITING GRAMMAR-TRANSLATION AND INDEPENDENT LEARNING METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE NEW NORMAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The teachers need to continually determine and decide on the kind of pedagogy that they are using to meet the needs of the learners. Educational pursuit amid and after pandemic should not only be a government's concern, rather, this also includes educators, particularly to those who actively engage in teaching. Thus, Revisiting Grammar Translation and Independent Learning Methods in Teaching Junior High School English for the 21st Century Education in the New Normal was conducted to come up with common strategies supportive of the pedagogy that suit to the current educational setting. Respondents of the study were the randomly selected 266 Junior High School Learners. Self-made questionnaires were used to gather necessary data to address the research problems consisting of four major parts revisiting the description of Grammar Translation, strategies in learning JHS English, the extent of the student's belief in the importance of the use of Independent Learning strategies, issues and challenges in the utilization of said methods, and common strategies that are supportive of the pedagogy suited in the new normal of the 21st-century education. As a result of revisiting, ten teaching strategies were confirmed to be supportive of the pedagogy that suit the new normal of 21st-century education. As an output, the Matrix of Strategies in Teaching English in the New Normal (MSTENN) was proposed for utilization.

Keywords: *21st Century Education, Grammar-Translation, Independent Learning, New Normal Pedagogy, Strategies in Teaching Junior High School English*

INTRODUCTION

The New Normal Education brings global challenges to the people, specifically the academe sectors had a sudden educational makeshift. Educational institutions find means and ways to address the issues by providing exhausting possible resources so that the quality of education is not compromised. Because of these, the teaching-learning processes also encountered problems that burden the teachers and the students. UNESCO (2017), stated that learning must continue because education cannot wait. After all, the world does not want to lose human capital. Likewise, teachers must recognize their roles in the process of adjustments. Department of Education (2020), said that they need to work harder and more creatively to carry out the objectives set of education.

The teaching in the new normal differs due to some practices which were no longer applicable and relevant at present; thus, there was a shift in the pedagogy to make the necessary adjustments. Cooper,(2022) confirmed that teachers are progressively advancing their teaching strategies in line with evidence-based practices and their student's learning needs. They need to be considerate of students' points of view to realize truly learner-centered instruction that utilizes teaching methods and strategies based on students' positive reception and acceptance. Hence, one of the teachers most relevant responses to the instruction challenges in the present is to initiate revisiting various teaching methods and strategies. It would help them adapt to the current instructional milieu and to be able to serve education in the most viable possible way.

While teachers are busy preparing their modules for Modular Distance Learning in a print medium, they continually experience a dilemma with some aspects of teaching. Most of these teachers' present apprehensions are regarding those practices that are hard to reconcile with those observances in instruction during the face-to-face classes when there were no threats of COVID-19 yet. Consequently, the bright side that the COVID-19 crisis presented points to the opportunity for the education sectors and partakers to come together, forge connections and share what works Obana,(2020). With the increasing need to make the Modular Distance Learning-Print (MDL-P) a more adequate and effective tool in teaching, there should also be an accumulating need to adjust teaching methodologies for teachers to employ relevant strategies that support learning in the current situation. Thus, Revisiting Grammar-Translation Method and Independent Learning in Teaching English in the New Normal education became an ever-relevant factor to account for with the usual strategies supportive of the pedagogy that suits the current educational setting.

With the realities and demands of the new normal, students are the direct targets affected by the abrupt changes and challenges. They often encountered difficulties understanding the modules written in English, accomplishing heavily loaded tasks provided in their self-learning modules, doing seemingly child-centered activities, and learning vocabulary and literature, as well as grammar and composition. These challenges emerged as the outcome of the shift in the focus of DepEd learning competencies prescribed by the newly adopted Curriculum Guide setting as Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs).

The initial implementation of the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan of the DepEd, considered successful as marked by the carrying out of its objectives in the School Year 2020-2021, there is an emerging need for continual adjustments to bring out the quality

of education being aspired for by the country. Parents and students pleaded for instruction more fitting for the learners amid the specific situations that prohibited the face-to-face delivery of teaching-learning processes. Learners particularly longed for Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) that are more considerate of their difficult learning situations.

In addition, most of the parents admitted their limitations to make the teaching facilitation roles with the right and expected outputs that would be the top concern of the teachers. Thus, this study which focuses on review of the use of Grammar Translation and Independent Learning Methods was conducted. It sought to determine whether application of embedded strategies would help carry out lessons in English. It also elaborated the two methods in teaching: to identify the extent of the importance of the strategies utilization, review common issues and concerns among revisited strategies, and name the common strategies supportive of the pedagogy that suits the new normal in teaching. As an output, a matrix of the styles found by learners supportive of the pedagogy that befit the new normal education emerged.

The study was conducted among the students to 824 learners that are 60% of this population belongs to the indigenous, while the remaining percent belongs to non-native lowland learners. The school implemented Modular Distance Learning-Print (MDLP) wherein learners are Home-schooled through the provided Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) with their parents, who are most of them, if not illiterate, have limited educational backgrounds.

Research Questions

This study aimed to revisit the Grammar Translation and Independent Learning Methods in Teaching Junior High School English, analyze issues and concerns on common strategies revisited, and identify which strategies under these methods are supportive of pedagogy that suits the new normal learning.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How are the common strategies on the Grammar-Translation Method described in terms of:
 - 1.1 teaching vocabulary through wordlists and translation;
 - 1.2 reading literary passage with reading comprehension questions;
 - 1.3 practicing translation of texts to and from Mother Tongue;
 - 1.4 elaborating presentation of grammar rules;
 - 1.5 memorizing grammar rules and vocabulary;
 - 1.6 including antonyms and synonyms, definitions, and other vocabulary exercises based on words in reading texts; and
 - 1.7 providing composition exercises based on topics from reading texts?
2. To what extent Independent Learning Method is used in terms of:
 - 2.1 reflection;
 - 2.2 feedback; and
 - 2.3 decision?

3. What issues and concerns are experienced by learners regarding the use of Grammar Translation and Independent Learning methods in teaching Junior High School English?
4. Based on learners' perspective, which among the strategies of Grammar-Translation and Independent Learning Methods are considered supportive of the pedagogy that suits the new normal education?
5. Based on the results of the study, what teaching strategies be proposed.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design. Mertler (2016), defined a descriptive research study aims to describe and interpret the status of individuals, settings, conditions, or events. It used a survey rather than an observation technique. The respondents were 266 Junior High School students who were chosen using the simple random sampling technique, and a self-made survey questionnaire was also used to gather necessary data. Gay et.al, (2012), described survey research primarily with the involvement of the collection of data to test premises or to answer questions about people's opinions regarding topics or issues and concerns. To establish reliability and validity, the instrument underwent the necessary procedures including test-retest validation with the aid of the t-test observing the .05 margin of error. Moreover, necessary communications, consents, and permits were observed and secured as deemed needed being an integral part of the processes of inquiry. The data gathered were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted.

RESULTS

1. Describing common strategies on Grammar Translation Method (GTM)

Table 1.1 Teaching vocabulary through wordlist and translation

Items	Weighted Mean	Rank	Description
1. Presents list of words to learn from the reading text or selection	3.14	2	Useful
2. Provides translation of words from English to Filipino	3.17	1	Useful
3. Indicates translation of words from Filipino to English	3.11	6.5	Useful
	1265		

4. Posts list of words to learn for every lesson being presented	3.11	6.5	Useful
5. Asks to translate words to the known language	3.12	4	Useful
6. Instructs to keep a list of words and their meaning	3.11	6.5	Useful
7. Requires a notebook intended for vocabulary learning/exercises	3.11	6.5	Useful
8. Prepares vocabulary listing for every lesson being studied	3.13	3	Useful
Overall mean	3.13	Useful	Useful

Table 1.1 showed that in opposition to the usual practice and principles on the instruction of the Second Language (L2), wherein the target language is taught solidly in the instruction process, learners are convinced that it is the other way round. The overall mean of 3.13 indicates that teaching vocabulary through wordlist and translation as part of Grammar Translation's strategies in Teaching English is generally functional, and noted that wordlist and translation are complementary ways of learning vocabulary.

Table 1.2 Description of Reading Literary Passages

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Includes reading materials from any literature	3.23	4	Useful
2. Uses reading comprehension questions to check understanding	3.14	6	Useful
3. Asks to answer questions every after reading	3.28	1	Useful
4. Strengthens understanding of the reading text through guide questions	3.27	2	Useful
5. Gives importance to reading and literature	3.17	5	Useful
6. Present literary piece regardless of length and encourages reading and understanding	3.08	7	Useful
7. Utilizes questions to guide learners in reading activity	3.26	3	Useful

8. Incorporates literature in every lesson taught	3.05	8	Useful
Overall Mean	3.19		Useful

The overall mean score of 3.19 describes the reading of literary passages, even at low levels, with reading comprehension questions to be functional. As stated, despite learners' seemingly observable apprehension towards incorporating literature in every lesson, the students understand the value of using comprehension questions in reading activities. The overall impression maintained the affirmation of the mentioned strategy, although there is a dichotomy between the students' resistance and their actual perception.

Table 1.3 Description of Practicing Based on Translation of Texts

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Provides exercises that allow learners to use own language to express ideas	2.88	7	Useful
2. Offers activities that encourage translation to and from learner's own language	2.84	8	Useful
3. Asks students to translate words/phrase/sentence to and from English	3.11	5	Useful
4. Encourages learners to understand lesson and relates it to equivalents in own language	3.24	2	Useful
5. Allows students to use Mother Tongue in answering comprehension questions	3.18	4	Useful
6. Gives exercises that allow translation of the reading text from English to Filipino	3.07	6	Useful
7. Permits the use of own language in explaining concepts learned from the reading text	3.25	1	Useful
8. Encourages learners to translate answers from own language to English	3.22	3	Useful
Overall Mean	3.10		Useful

The computed overall mean score of 3.10 revealed that practicing based on the translation of the text to and from the Mother Tongue is useful in teaching English. As noted, students consider it helpful when the teacher permits the use of their language in explaining concepts learned from the reading text. Despite this, learners do not want teachers to prepare extra activities specifically for translation to and from the Mother Tongue.

Table 1.4 Description of Elaborating Presentation of Grammar Rules

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Presents clear explanation on principles of grammar being taught	3.23	3.5	Useful
2. Demonstrates grammar rules through examples	3.08	6.5	Useful
3. Uses illustrations to present clearly the grammatical concepts	3.08	6.5	Useful
4. Provides complete discussions and details of grammar rules being studied	3.23	3.5	Useful
5. Address complex grammar rules and principles with emphasis	3.24	2	Useful
6. Intensifies grammar rules learning and mastery through progressive exercises	3.06	7	Useful
7. Gives particular reminders on grammar rules exceptions when they should be remembered	3.27	1	Useful
8. Contrasts grammar rules of the target language to the grammar rules of own language	3.03	8	Useful

Overall Mean	3.15	Useful	
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The overall mean score of 3.15 signified that elaborating the presentation of grammar rules is useful for English teaching. Generally, it underlined the importance of clear explanations on the intricacy of grammar rules in English.

Table 1.5 Description of Memorizing Grammar Rules and Vocabulary

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Guides learners to memorize grammar rules and vocabulary	3.18	3.5	Useful
2. Instructs students to master a list of words with their meanings	3.23	2	Useful
3. Gives activities to check the level of student's mastery of grammar rules and vocabulary	3.18	3.5	Useful
4. Checks mastery of grammar rules through the provided activities	3.15	6.5	Useful
5. Emphasizes to the learners the value of memorizing rules and vocabulary	3.15	6.5	Useful
6. Sets mastery of grammar rules and vocabulary as part of subject requirements	3.24	1	Useful
7. Devotes specific part of the lesson for memorization of grammar rules and vocabulary	2.89	8	Useful
8. Employs memorization as technique of learning grammar concepts and vocabulary	3.17	5	Useful
Overall Mean	3.23		Useful

The

computed overall mean score of 3.23 revealed that student memorization of grammar rules and vocabulary is useful in teaching Junior High School English and setting mastery

of grammar rules and vocabulary as part of subject requirements was described by learners as useful.

Table 1.6 Description of Including Vocabulary Exercises

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Includes exercises on synonyms and antonyms for vocabulary mastery	3.23	2	Useful
2. Incorporates definition of words for vocabulary learning	3.06	6	Useful
3. Provides vocabulary exercises on words coming from the reading texts	3.05	7	Useful
4. Lead students to explore other meanings of words through synonyms and antonyms	3.26	1	Useful
5. Presents activities focused on vocabulary found in the reading text with their meanings	3.12	4	Useful
6. Emphasizes activities for vocabulary mastery in the lesson	2.86	8	Useful
7. Asks students to define words lifted from the literature being studied	3.10	5	Useful
8. Identifies words from the selection which meaning students need to know	3.15	3	Useful
Overall Mean	3.10		Useful

The overall mean score of 3.10 revealed that vocabulary exercises including antonyms and synonyms, definitions, and others based on words in reading texts was described as useful.

Table 1.7 Description of Providing Composition Exercises

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Includes composition exercises relevant with the reading text	2.87	8	Useful
2. Prepares writing activities based on the given topics	3.26	1.5	Useful
3. Offers opportunity for writing every after reading activity	3.26	1.5	Useful
4. Uses the theme of the reading selection as subject of the composition exercises	3.11	3	Useful
5. Motivates writing interest through appreciation of the literature being read	2.95	6	Useful
6. Performs writing exercises to critic reading materials	2.94	7	Useful
7. Suggests writing themes taken from the topics of the reading text	3.01	4	Useful
8. Requires composition writing as an important course requirement in English	2.99	5	Useful
Overall Mean	3.04		Useful

Results revealed that students were convinced that preparing writing activities based on the topic of the given selection and offering the students opportunity for writing every after reading are vital in learning the English language. This finding emphasized that learners are inclined to integrating what they have learned into their real-life experiences through writing as shown in the overall computed mean score of 3.04

2. Extent of importance of independent learning with its selected common strategies used

Table 2.1 Extent of importance of reflection as Independent Learning strategy

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Executes reflection as part of diagnostic activities	3.06	6	High
2. Does reflection as formative part of the lesson	3.05	7.5	High
3. Writes reflection as part of assessment of learning	3.28	1	High
4. Integrates reflection as an important process of learning	3.09	3	High
5. Devotes specific time for reflection in each lesson	3.07	5	High
6. Encourages to reflect on the content of the lesson	3.11	4	High
7. Establishes mastery of the lesson through reflection	3.05	7.5	High
8. Strengthens learning plans through reflections	3.12	2	High
Overall Mean	3.04		High

Having the overall mean score of 3.10, the results revealed that writing reflection as part of the assessment of learning was perceived by learners to be with high extent of importance. This finding indicates that learners recognize the value of doing reflection as evaluative part of learning journey.

Table 2.2 Importance of Feedback as Independent Learning Strategy

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Corrects on reading comprehension activities through given feedback	3.29	3	High
2. Utilizes feedback on grammar and vocabulary exercises	3.09	5	High
3. Improves composition writing skills through feedback given	3.28	4	High
4. Develops positive attitudes towards language study through feedback	3.34	1	High
5. Applies corrections obtained through given feedback	3.05	6	High
6. Seeks feedback from peers and others to strengthen learning	2.86	7	High
7. Boosts learning opportunities through healthy feedback communication	3.33	2	High
8. Communicates feedback in a constructive manner	2.85	8	High
Overall Mean	3.14		High

The overall mean score obtained was 3.14 indicated that learners value feedback as part of the learning process, regardless how it is given to them.

Table 1. Importance of Decision as Independent Learning Strategy

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Has the freedom to decide which learning activities to do	3.27	2	High
2. Decides on which materials to use for effective learning	3.07	3.5	High

3. Takes responsibility for every learning tasks	3.29	1	High	
4. Observes own pacing for the learning processes	3.07	3.5	High	
5. Sets own learning targets and makes own learning plan	2.95	8	High	
6. Appraises learning progress through self-assessment	2.97	7	High	
7. Distinguishes helpful inputs from not helpful ones	3.04	6	High	
8. Chooses which tool to use to assess one's learning	3.25	3	High	The
Overall Mean	3.14		High	

result revealed that taking responsibility for every learning task was described as high extent of importance with the overall mean score of 3.11. This demonstrated that learners are interested to be empowered as they undertake their learning tasks.

3. Issues and concerns on the use of Grammar-Translation and Independent Learning Methods in teaching Junior High School English

Table 3.1 Issues and concerns on Grammar Translation Method

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Focuses merely on translation	3.10	3.5	Manifested
2. Gives prime importance only to reading and writing but neglects speaking and listening	3.09	5	Manifested
3. Employs teacher-centered instruction	3.28	2	Manifested
4. Emphasizes memorization as best approach to master grammar rules and vocabulary	3.10	3.5	Manifested
5. Allows the use of mother tongue in teaching English	3.29	1	Manifested

6. Teaches vocabulary through lists of isolated words	3.08	6	Manifested
7. Neglects context of texts in the study of literature	3.07	7	Manifested
8. Neglects pronunciation	2.30	8	Less Manifested
Overall Mean	3.04		Manifested

The overall mean of score of 3.04 revealed that most students confirmed manifestation of the issues and concerns raised on the use of the said method based on their current experience in English language instruction.

Table 3.2 Issues and Concerns on Independent Learning

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Considers setting self-learning goals difficult	3.29	1	Manifested
2. Can do self-assessment in a dishonest manner	2.85	7	Manifested
3. Lacks interest in doing reflection	2.82	8	Manifested
4. Depends highly on feedback of teachers and peers	3.08	3.5	Manifested
5. Affects quality of learning outcomes when given too much freedom	3.07	5	Manifested
6. Fails to use genuine materials when not guided by teachers	3.06	6	Manifested
7. Tends to choose only easy learning tasks or activities	3.09	2	Manifested
8. Doubts on the fairness of the method for all types of learners	3.08	3.5	Manifested
Overall Mean	3.04		Manifested

The overall mean score of 3.04 confirmed that all the named common issues and concerns under the Independent Learning were manifested based on the respondents' experiences.

Table 4. 1 Common Strategies in Teaching Junior High School English

Items	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Teaching vocabulary through wordlists and translation	3.20	3.5	Supportive
2. Reading of literary passages with reading comprehension questions	3.20	3.5	Supportive
3. Practicing translation of texts to and from Mother Tongue	3.19	6.5	Supportive
4. Elaborating presentation of grammar rules and vocabulary	3.20	3.5	Supportive
5. Memorizing grammar rules and vocabulary	3.19	6.5	Supportive
6. Providing composition exercises based on the reading texts	3.20	3.5	Supportive
7. Including vocabulary exercises on antonyms, synonyms, and definitions others based on words in reading texts	3.17	9	Supportive
8. Using reflection as part of learning process	3.10	10	Supportive
9. Employing feedback regularly to improve learning outcomes	3.18	8	Supportive
10. decide for their own learning goals	3.26	1	Supportive
Overall Mean	3.19		Supportive

The overall mean score of 3.19 described the common strategies in teaching Junior High School English as supportive of pedagogy that suits the new normal education. As data disclosed, Grammar-Translation and Independent Learning Methods are employing strategies that are relevant to the learning needs of the students at present.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicated in table 1.1, are substantially consistent with what Mart, (2013) said that translation is an aid to enhance proficiency via the target language. According to him, translation is functional in understanding another language studied. It claimed that the Grammar-Translation method indeed is supportive and has a unique role in foreign

language learning that it allows the students to distinguish the differences and similarities between the first language (L1) and the second language (L2), making the students comprehend better light the system of the target language. To support, Kaye,(2021) pointed out that most English Language teachers and theorists nowadays recognize the “validity and value” of translation as strategies in teaching. Designing translation activities well for instruction can hone multiple language learning skills, particularly in the vocabulary aspect. Translation is essential in developing communicative competence, because it demands accuracy, clarity, and flexibility. It was further pointed out that translation trains the reader to search (which is an act of exercising flexibility) for the best words’ equivalent (which is an act of valuing accuracy) to communicate the meaning (which is an act of venturing on clarity).

The table 1.2 adheres to relevant guidelines set by the DepEd (Department of Education, (2020) stipulating that the learning competency shall be sub-tasked if it is necessary to allow the learners to easily follow the lesson’s progression, following the principles of mastery learning. Engaging students to interact with the literature by asking them to answer given questions after reading was indeed said to be helpful for language learning. The same finding is relevant to what Bowen, (2016) stated that using more enlightened principles while combining them with the systematic approach of Grammar Translation suited learning needs and styles of various learners. This indicates that fluency takes place through reading literary passages after reading in the target language.

The table 1.3 means that respondents believe in the unique role of translation in the teaching-learning process though they do not want their teachers to devise separate activities plainly devoted for translation. This result is supportive of what Khan,(2018) found out that GTM is a very useful method for learners to learn English where learning becomes easy and advantageous noting that learners find hard time learning English through other presently trending methods like direct method and audio-lingual method emphasizing the drawback of the absence of English-speaking communit

In.elaborating presentation of grammar rules, the finding is consistent with Aqel,(2013) found that language skills acquisition and the mastery of the grammatical rules must also be focused on, thus, commending the application of grammatical structure and the practicing of the language skills in general at the target language as to strengthen the required forms that the students need to develop to succeed in the learning of the target language. In this way, learners enjoy the great benefit of full knowledge of the two languages alongside which liberates the students from any tendency of ambiguity of the language being studied. In addition, Chang,(2011) affirmed that being given the significant and necessary elaboration, learners will try to refrain from committing possible the same errors when using the target language and when errors take place, the students are already capable of giving reasons why avoiding repetitive mistakes, as a result. In the light of this finding, it is an important consideration to keep abreast with various activities that could be best employed to making the elaborate presentation of grammar rules more interesting to the learners.

Based from the results from table 1.5, it revealed that learners are more inclined to highlighting the importance of mastering grammar as significant component of language English learning in Junior High School This result directs teachers to set certain learning

rules among their students that emphasize the mastery of grammar and vocabulary. However, as result implied there is no necessity to devoting specific parts of the lesson for plain memorization purposes. This finding reiterated that while students remained to be in good esteem with the usefulness of memorizing grammar rules and vocabulary in learning the English Language, learners understand that it should not be done separately from each part but along with the lesson, Garlock,(2019) claimed that memorization in the context of formal education setting booster learning outcomes. Therefore, as the current research advocates its proper use, memorization which is usually involving a process employing techniques of repetition for mastery becomes an effective propeller to language mastery.

Table 1.6 result emphasized that learners expect their teachers to prepare lessons more on leading and allowing them to discover vocabulary meanings through various exercises like synonyms and antonyms, the definition of words, guided simulations about meanings, and reading text-driven vocabulary exercises. The results implied that students remained to have good esteem with the incorporation of vocabulary exercises in the lesson which is highly based on the selection embedded in the lesson. This result is conforming with the idea on vocabulary integration that taking vocabulary as the core consideration in teaching all grade levels. This entails activities that go beyond vocabulary familiarization and memorization aiming to integrate vocabulary words into learners' language patterns. Thus, it affirms activities that require the application of the learned vocabulary terms in various vehicles of learners' communication as well as remembering the value of word identification activities suggesting that teachers could guide learners to decode words from a given material honing the skills for word identification which consequently leads to stronger functional language used among learners. Using activities on vocabulary exercises make the learners critical ones in understanding and improving their vocabulary skills like what Ilter,(2019) confirmed in his study that doing this has a meaningful impact on learners' comprehension and increasing their proficiency and building the students' vocabularies.

In table 1.7, students, however, expect their teachers to engage them in writing activities that are not solely confined within the theme of the reading text used. While they recognize the value of relating the theme of the selection in their own lives, learners prefer writing activities for free self-expression. Considering this, it is important that composition writing be given particular importance as part of instruction. This kind of activity helps students crystallize and articulate the text's ideas so that they can explore them further. Moreover, activities like this, as Gibson,(2021) recommended, to remind teachers to provide learners high levels of a support system as they engage in the process. In addition, Ball,et.al (2021), noted that designing exercises like this is helpful to roll information providing insight on certain aspects of the story embedded in a literature read. In such manner, the learners are allowed to relay their insights and understanding as well as their opinions or reflection on the given text.

Table 2.1 Extent of importance of reflection as Independent Learning strategy indicates that learners recognize the value of doing reflection as evaluative part of learning journey. It also showed that students are more inclined to reflect as part of the assessment rather than doing it as part of the formative assessment. The finding noted the need for teachers to provide learners time for reflection as part of learning assessment, basis to strengthen

learning plans, deepen important part of the learning process, and understand the content of the lesson. This result is conforming to Cavilla,(2017) claimed that through reflection, learners can develop their ability to actualize the insights they gained into their learning or life experience so that they can do better and level up their learning performances.

The findings show the importance of feedback as independent learning strategy. The learners are more concerned with the availability of feedback because they consider them as part of the independent learning process. The result of this study conforms with the DepEd Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in the Light of Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan stipulating that immediate feedback should be made accessible to the learners to enable them to take full responsibility for their learning and identify areas where they do well and where they need help. Double et al. (2020), revealed that feedback is considered the central component of the learning process which is vital for students' knowledge acquisition and learning progress.

As conveyed, taking responsibility caught the students' closer attention because learners sensed beneficial impact of this practice in their learning performance and outcomes. When learners have full freedom, they also learn to be more responsible for the things they do and accountable of the outcomes. This could also noted that decision-making is an important strategy in independent learning as perceived by learners. This result implied that students learn best when they are given full authority for the decisions they make towards learning. Expressively however, they are not inclined to setting their learning targets and making their learning plans. This finding is highly congruent with Schmitz,(2018), claimed that good decision making is a skill that is essential. This is affirmative with the claim that there is a strong need for individuals who can independently make a good decision nowadays. Improving students means improving their decision-making skills. As clearly affirmed, decision-making must be an important part of teaching using the Independent Learning Method Enriquez,(2018), found out that giving students freedom to decide or choose whatever kind of task or activity they want to engage in relevant with the set learning goals or objectives.

Table 3.1 revealed the Issues and concerns on Grammar Translation Method in which manifestation is considered a product of the learners' previous experiences as well as understanding of the factors influencing their behavior towards the issues and concerns being pointed out. This finding confirmed the issues and concerns raised on the utilization of Grammar Translation Method focuses merely on translation, gives only prime importance to reading and writing but neglects speaking and listening, employs teacher-centered instruction, and emphasizes memorization as best approach to master grammar rules and vocabulary. In addition to these issues, Abbas et al. (2014) signified that the method employs teaching of vocabulary through lists of isolated words and neglecting context of the texts in the study of literature. Although it could be deduced that the emergence of the articulated issues was prior to the pandemic, the manifestations remained to be the same articulating possible drawbacks with the utilization of GTM when not done in a more directed manner. Aqel,(2013) confirmed that utilization of this method should be dynamic and situational.

As regards to the Issues and concerns on independent learning, it is attributed to the learners being used to the kind of instruction readily and constantly directed and guided by

the teachers with a prototype learning process set for them with a conventional setting prior to pandemic. Manifestation on lack of interest in doing reflection was also noted. This result entailed students' perceived difficulty in doing reflection as part of instruction. This difficulty is associated with the lack of understanding of the value of self-reflection and its advantages in the learning process. Students also experienced difficulties in the process relative to lack of readily available guidance, tedious compliance to obligatory reflection writing requirements, and traumatic experience relative to reflection. Other things mentioned were doing self-assessment in a dishonest manner, depending highly on feedback of teachers and peers, affecting quality of learning outcomes when given too much freedom, failing to use genuine materials when not guided by teachers, tending to choose only easy learning tasks or activities, and doubting the fairness of the method for all types of learners. Relevant with this finding, teachers are reminded of "the black holes" in Independent Learning that Foley, (2016) commented on claiming that doing Independent Learning is knowing where teachers need to focus. As expressed, teachers need to find out the key factors on social, cultural, and environmental aspects that describe to what extent of independent learning the learners do actualize, while learners are convinced of the usefulness of Independent Learning Method's utilization. They also acknowledged the disadvantageous side described by the level of manifestations obtained with the use of the method.

The findings revealed that the strategies are deciding for learning goal, doing reflection, advocating vocabulary learning through wordlists and translation, reading of literary passages even at low levels with reading comprehension questions, practicing translation of texts to and from Mother Tongue, elaborating presentations of grammar rules, teaching through memorization, giving composition exercises based on topics from the reading texts, including vocabulary exercises on antonyms, synonyms, and definitions. Likewise, reflection, reading texts, and giving feedback regularly and decision to improve learning outcomes are also contributing factors. . Concerning these findings, Vega, (2018) confirmed that despite the benefits of translation many linguists and teachers oppose the utilization of this method. There are linguists and grammarians who promote teaching without translating. Azar et.al (2012) insisted that grammar teaching should be done in explicit and implicit ways but without using translation. This position however is contested by the current study revealing students' favorable reception of the use of strategies under Grammar Translation Method at present. More than this, the use of the Independent Learning method is also reaffirmed for its obvious benefits.

Based on the results, students recognized the use of teaching strategies employed under Grammar Translation and Independent Learning Methods as supportive to the pedagogy the suits the new normal set-up. Respective of these results, this study proposed the conceptualization and construction of a matrix for the use of strategies under these methods which would be beneficial to ensuring that teaching Junior High School English in the new normal setting is done relevantly. The matrix is anchored with the Department of Education's Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). Specifically, the matrix covers 10 strategies usable in teaching English across all grade levels in the four learning quarters of a School Year.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, strategies in teaching under the Grammar Translation and Independent Learning Methods were described as useful and highly important, respectively. Most of the common revisited issues and concerns were manifested except the issue on pronunciation. All the strategies employed under the Grammar Translation and Independent Learning Methods are supportive of the pedagogy that suits the new normal of 21st-century education. Therefore, there is an implied need to use a matrix of teaching strategies for the utilization of Grammar Translation and Independent Learning methods.

Recommendations

Given these findings and conclusions, teachers may use strategies employed under Grammar-Translation and Independent Learning Methods. With this, learners, parents, and guardians may be constantly encouraged to be guided by the principles of Grammar-Translation and Independent Learning Methods to avoid the drawbacks relative with the various issues and concerns revisited and to maximize the benefits of utilization. Learners' Materials (LMs) developers and teachers may use the Matrix of Strategies in Teaching English in the New Normal (MSTENN) to ensure that their teaching strategies employ techniques and activities for learning relevant with the current educational setting.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The utmost level of confidentiality was upheld for all data gathered for this study. Every participant's voluntary engagement was given a high priority including their withdrawal at any time they wish to. Furthermore, the researchers ensured that all the participants were properly oriented and assured that all of the data and results obtained were not disclosed in unauthorized persons and used for the intended purpose only.

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